

Perceptual Study Regarding the Impact of Recreational Activities Upon Healthy Lifestyle of Youth

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Abstract: *The main focus of the existing research study was to examine the impact of recreational activities upon youth from social prospective healthy lifestyle. The study Population consist of 520 Teachers, 15890 Students and 14926Parents from Government Girls Colleges (GGC), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Five districts Swabi, Peshawar, Kohat, Lakki Marwat and Dera Ismail Khan (20% percent of 25 districts) were randomly selected from the population further the researcher using proportionate sampling technique for the data collection. Self- developed and administered questionnaire was used for the present study to draw finding and conclusion. Both descriptive frequency and percentage and inferential statistic was used for such as regression and ANOVA were used for the data analysis. It was concluded that the researcher concluded that a very positive stance was received regarding effectiveness of recreation in individual lives and particularly among the youngster. The respondents of all categories i.e. parents, students and teachers thought that recreation is very effective tool to promote and develop healthy lifestyle.*

Key Words: Recreational Activities, Healthy Lifestyle And Youth

Introduction

Any attractive and pleasurable work that we perform in our spare time and chose it according to will and wishes is called recreation. According to Scott and Shafer (2001) recreational activities assist the participant in developing healthy life style, moreover it make a person the functional member of the society. [McKnight & Kashdan \(2009\)](#) found that living a healthy life is a primary factor to get the overall fitness and happiness. A healthy lifestyle is one which helps to keep and improve people's health and well-being. According to [Clark and Oswald \(2002\)](#) physical activity and recreation are the basic way of improving healthy life style of an individual, similarly healthy life style enhances the prosperity and wellbeing. The author further suggested that several government and non-administrative relationship have attempted huge actions in solid way of life and wellbeing advancement for the betterment and prosperity of humanity. A healthy lifestyle helps in maintaining health standard and prevent from various diseases. For achievement of health, it is obligatory to have virtuous nutrition, daily exercise and satisfactory sleep. Similarly, [McKnight & Kashdan \(2009\)](#) analyze that a sound way of life abandons you fit, vigorous and helps in preventing from various diseases. The study further substantiates that prodigious nourishment; day by day exercise and satisfactory rest are the establishments for proceeding with great wellbeing. For a longer and comfortable life, it is also important to adopt the principles of a healthy lifestyle. [Kottler and Chen \(2007\)](#) in their study "Stress Management and Prevention" found that overseeing stress and anxiety in positive way, rather than through drug abuse, drinking liquor and smoking reduce wear and tear on your body at the hormonal level and to live perfect life, set up together your arrangement for a healthy way of life.

Adaptation of healthy habits leads to healthy life style. Good habits like constructive use of leisure time, appropriate sleeping habits, regular work out and timely taking food and participation

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in some activities are considered to be healthy habits (Kemper, 2010). For effective and productive healthy life style, adaptation of these habits is very much important. Participation in an organized program of recreation activities provide an opportunities through which one can develop and maintain healthy habits which leads to healthy life style (Fraser-Thomas, Côté&Deakin, 2005).

In this connection, Mannell (2007) stated that Healthy life style is heavily dependent upon leisure and recreation as these are considered to be crucial for human being. The author further stated that Relaxation, rest and revitalization through meaningful leisure help in building positive self-image and work as an active source of self-esteem in addition to management of stress in today's busy and demanding life. Similarly, Kim, Woo&Uysal (2015) concluded that Participation in recreational activities contributes significantly to individual and community life. They further substantiated that recreational activities adds to people's quality of life. The study also illustrated that Engagement in recreational activities as well as having balanced diet and constructive use of leisure time leads to a healthy lifestyle, another important element of social perspective is socialization. Socialization is the process of taking guidance and knowledge regarding code of conduct, customs and traditions for becoming a functional member of the society. Socialization is the product of involvement of individuals in different activities as there are many activities in which individuals take part. Recreational activities offer ample opportunities for every individual to indulge him/herself. According to Godbey (2009) recreation offers the chance for socialization. The author further elaborated the significance of recreational activities in relation to socialization that these activities reflects the existing cultural values of the society and also helps in pattern maintenance and tension management.

Problem statement

Inactivity is always considered as a serious threatened to various aspects of humans. No matter it is health related issues, societal issues or even the life style of individuals. One of the main reasons behind these issues is less availability of recreational opportunities. Recreation is a physical activity in which the people get together, share their happy moments, which aim to reduce the fatigue, physical and mental exertion and to eliminate stress. The researcher is of the opinion that the people of the concerned locality and particularly the female section is facing with different health and other problems. If attention in this regard, is not given, and do not come up with suitable measures, then the situation will leads to worst condition. On the other hand students, parents and teachers may play a significant role in diverting the attention of masses towards these problems. Therefore, it is very much important to understand the perception of students, parents and teachers, about the impact of recreational activities among youth from social perspective. These thought provoking points made the researcher decided to conduct a gender based study by including female teachers, students and parents for the exploration of the most relevant aspects in the society and to get their response regarding the benefits of recreation. The title suggested for the study is, "The Impact of Recreational Activities upon Healthy Lifestyle of Youth".

Objective of the Study

To investigate the impact of recreational activities upon healthy lifestyle of youth

Literature Review

In the modern area of technology, most of the people are suffering from variety of complication and problems, leads to different psychological diseases. Participating in sporting events and recreational activities is most effective way to eliminate psychological problem and improve healthy life style. Recreation have very important role in modern society, some of the main functions are classified here as under.

There are long lasting and considerable benefits of recreational activities which promoting the healthy life style way. Healthy lifestyle can be categorized into the below terms. Healthy life style is an obligatory principal to have optimal health and well-being. There may be different factors which

influence one health and health well-being. Those people who indulge in unhealthy habits prone to various disease and such habits dis-standardize their health and happiness. A research conducted by Kaiser and Allen (2002) found that unhealthy habits like smoking, poor diet, sedentary way of life and destructive thoughts leads to premature health decline and death. There are many aspects play pivotal role in maintaining and achieving overall health. In this regard, [Rock et al. \(2012\)](#) found that proper diet, physical activity and proper reset contribute to overall health and quality of life. Similarly, [Kumanyika et al. \(2008\)](#) states that taking sound and balance diet helps in maintaining energy level throughout the day which helps in overall health and happiness whereas, William et al. (2007) argues that participation in various aerobic and strength activities, control weight gain and helps in controlling and minimizing chronic conditions. In a similar study, Lichtenstein et al. (2006) found that healthy life style habits like adequate nutrition, limiting alcohol intake and junk food contribute to a healthy life. The author suggested that the proper amount of rest and balance diet is too one the key factors of healthy life style. To concentrate on the healthy lifestyle, keeping into view the quality of life, proper diet, physical activity allow you to live more and serve best. In this regard, [Schwartz and McCarthy \(2007\)](#) in a study “Manage your energy, not your time” states that concentrating on a solid way of life enhances your personal satisfaction, as well as it might include years too. [Peterson, Ruch, Beermann, Park & Seligman \(2007\)](#) argues that proper awareness about your eating regimen, physical movement and anxiety levels permits you to successfully adjust all parts of your life and might build your life range. He further find out that that keeping up customary physical examinations helps with early location and treatment of medicinal conditions. Likewise, your specialist can prescribe way of life propensities that add to a more drawn out and more beneficial life. It is nature of human physiology that after a difficult day of work or concentrate, the person concerned feel anxious and then the body needs to do something different. In any case, the best advantages of recreational activity happen to be anxiety alleviation. [Wiedenman \(2019\)](#) indicated that taking part in recreational activities assists in expanding the measure of norepinephrine in your mind and getting endorphins running can deal with a man's physical and mental anxiety mitigation. The author further suggested that whenever you are feeling sensibly exhausted, take the recreational exercise rather than into your bed. A review of current literature of [Street, James and Cutt \(2007\)](#) indicates that people who participate in sports clubs and organized recreational activity enjoy better mental health, are more alert, and more resilient against the stresses of modern living. Similarly [Bittman et al. \(2003\)](#) found that taking part in sporting events such as games, recreation, and exercise and play significant role in elucidating anxiety, stress and so many psychological problems and develop physical and mental health.

Theoretical Framework

Hypothesis of the Study

Recreational activities have significant impact upon healthy life style of its participants.

Method and Martial

The present study aimed to investigate the impact of recreational activities upon youth from social prospective healthy lifestyle. The study Population consist of 520 Teachers, 15890 Students and 14926 Parents from Government Girls Colleges (GGC), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Five districts Swabi, Peshawar, Kohat, LakkiMarwat and Dera Ismail Khan (20% percent of 25 districts) were randomly selected from the population further the researcher using proportionate sampling technique for the

data collection. Self- developed and administered questionnaire was used for the present study to draw finding and conclusion. Research design is the plan, strategies or blue print carried out in advance for the research study (Osanloo& Grant2016) while Quantitative Research is a simple research method followed to quantify the phenomena by using numerical and statistics (McCusker&Gunaydin2015). Face and content validity was done from the expert in the field of sport sciences and physical education. Cronbach's Alpha method was used for questionnaire. Pilot testing was done prior to the data collection. The initially developed questionnaire was circulated among the 32 respondent, complication and ambiguities were removed according. Reliability result of Recreation Activities was .824 and the healthy life style was 876. The overall reliability result was 0.798. Both descriptive statistics like Frequencies and Percentages and inferential statistic such as regression and ANOVA were used for the data analysis. The researcher used quantitative method with cross-section research design for the present study to draw conclusion. The researcher started the data collection process during the month of January 2020 and completes his course in three months. The collected data were put in to statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version #24 and analyzed through variety of statistical tool/test to reach at certain findings and conclusion.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Statistics for Scales

S.No	Questionnaire	Items	Cronbach's alpha reliability
1	Recreation Activities	20	.824
2	Healthy Lifestyle	21	.876
	Total	41	.798

Empirical analyses of the study

Table 2. Category-Wise Frequencies and Percentages

		Teachers, Parents and Students			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valida	Teachers	103	3.2	3.2	3.2
	Parents	1589	49.1	49.1	52.2
	Students	1547	47.8	47.8	100.0
	Total	3239	100.0	100.0	

Bar-Graph Showing the Frequencies of Teachers, Parents And Students

Showing the frequencies and percentages of sample that the total number of Teachers is 103 and percentage is 3.2. The total frequency of parents is 1589 and percentage is 49.1. The total number of students is 1547 and percentage is 47.8. The total sample of the study is 3239.

Recreational Activities have Significant role Upon Healthy Life Style of its Participants.

Enter-Method regression showing the impact of recreational activities upon healthy life style

Table 3. Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.664 ^a	.441	.440	.92528

a. Predictors: (Constant), Recreational Activities

b. Dependent Variable: Healthy Lifestyle

Table 4. ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2183.381	1	2183.381	2.550E3	.000 ^a
	Residual	2771.347	3237	.856		
	Total	4954.729	3238			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Recreational Activities

b. Dependent Variable: Healthy Lifestyle

Table 5. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.225	.059		3.799	.000
	Recreational Activities	.931	.018	.664	50.500	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Healthy Lifestyle

Histogram of regression (Recreational activities, Healthy lifestyle)

Normal P-P Plot of regression Standardized Residual (Recreational activities, Healthy lifestyle)

The above table shows the Calculates that recreational activities have significant role upon healthy lifestyle of youth that the Adjusted R Square is .440 which shows that recreational activities have 44% effect on healthy lifestyle of youth. The B Positive seems .931 ($P < .01$) which indicates that 1 unit increase in recreational activities will cause .931 unit increase in healthy lifestyle of youth, in simple words 100 units increase in recreational activities will cause 93 % positive variation in healthy lifestyle of youth. While the alternative hypothesis stating significant role was found of recreational activities upon healthy lifestyle of youth is hereby accepted.

Result and Discussion

Recreational activities have significant impact upon healthy lifestyle of youth that the Adjusted R Square is .440 which shows that recreational activities have 44% effect on healthy lifestyle of youth. The B Positive seems .931 ($P < .01$) which indicates that 1 unit increase in recreational activities will cause .931 unit increase in healthy lifestyle of youth, in simple words 100 units increase in recreational activities will cause 93 % positive variation in healthy lifestyle of youth. While the alternative hypothesis stating significant role was found of recreational activities upon healthy lifestyle of youth is hereby accepted. Similarly, [Kaerney \(2002\)](#) declared that taking part in recreational events is the most effect way avoiding from malpractices and immoral activities such as drug abuse, gambling and smoking. In addition to, [Turi \(2012\)](#) highlighted that positive recreational activities develop and promote the key personality characteristic such as openness, agreeableness, extraversion etc. among those who take part in the recreational activities its participants. In the same line, [Mclean and Narcisi \(2005\)](#) clarify that exercise; play and recreation is the basic tool which promote one's physical and mental health. They also concluded that exercise; play and recreation develop some other qualities which are the attribute of healthy life style such as harmony, justice, brotherhood and equality which promote the good society.

The study revealed that the students, parents and teachers were of the view that recreational activities have positive effect in seeking social skills. Major portion of the population considered that taking part in recreational events develop social skills which enables an individual to cope within diverse conditions. These findings are well supported by [Mahoney; Harris&Eccles \(2006\)](#) found a very positive relationship between team based recreation and the development of leadership skills. Majority of the respondents were of the view that sports and recreational events quite helpful in the mental development, similar to the result of [Weng& Chiang \(2014\)](#) found that recreational and exercises activities have significant role in developing of physical and mental health. Similarly, [Murphy& Carbone \(2008\)](#) indicated that all those, who participate in exercise and recreational activates have strong mind capacity and strong deceive power.

Conclusions

The researcher concluded that a very positive stance was received regarding effectiveness of recreation in individual lives and particularly among the youngster. Respondent of all the categories of respondents i.e. students, teachers and parents thought that recreation is the very effective tool to promote and develop healthy life style. It was also concluded that recreational activity develop positive relationship between team based recreation and the development of leadership skills. On the basis of the finding it was also highlighted that recreational activity boosts immune system, blood pressure. The researcher also found that recreational activity building up the sense of co-operation, mutual understanding and exhibition of culture which leads to the process of socialization.

Study Contribution

In our society, it is the duty of our parents and teachers to promote the important of recreational activities. This study will help parents and teachers to convince and motivates their children towards active participation in organized recreational programs by providing the fruitful outcome of participation in these activities. Despite many social problems, some problems point to the high accident rate in the concerned area, due to the non or less availability of recreational activities and

the only solution to these problems is the provision of organized various recreational activities. The findings of the study will motivate the people to indulge themselves in recreational activities to develop healthy lifestyle.

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